

“The composer as vibe specialist” (An Audio-Visual Composition)

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Abstract

Apparently, the way of the future is by *vibing* with AI platforms, i.e., textually describing what one wants, waiting for the bespoke output, and finally taking pride in having created something. This work explores that future. More specifically, I describe to one platform the computer code I want it to generate (*vibecoding*) that I can use to remix video files in “artsy” ways. I describe to another platform what music audio I want it to generate (*vibesynthing*) to accompany a processed video file. I curate materials from the results and compile into short video works to mix together.

1 Method of composition

1.1 Vibecoding¹ visuals

I prompted an AI coding chatbot with the following vibe:

I need python code that will take a specified video file and chop it up randomly to create a new artsy video. It should be a command line program that accepts variables such as duration, minimum and maximum segment length, segment repetition probability, and outputs an mp4 video file.

I worked iteratively with the chatbot to get rid of errors in the code it generated, finally arriving to a working 131-line script. I then modified the script in a variety of ways (adding controls for random pitch shifts, image inversion, and time stretching) and experimented with it using a variety of video materials.

1.2 Vibesynthing audio

To create audio material for accompanying an “artsy video” created with the vibecoded script, I used the chopped-up soundtrack as context for a “remix” functionality on an AI music audio generation platform.² Some of the vibes I specified were:

- modern percussion corigliano electronic musical prog rock childrens circus
- slow slow slow drones organ music drones pads delicate
- silly kazoos, kids music, childplay, electric guitar
- dramatic orchestra soft pop introduction to huge act, drums and percussion, horns, exciting
- E L V I S, building sound, crescendo

¹ The term “vibecoding” was coined by Andrej Karpathy for the method of programming via interaction with a chatbot. One describes in text what one wants a computer program to do, to which the chatbot responds by writing the computer program.

² An “AI music audio generation platform” is an online service that generates music audio from context and textual descriptions, or vibes.

1.3 Composition

I curated material from the generated audio and compose with it in a digital audio workstation. I used Davinci Resolve to compile the video and audio material. Some stills are shown below, using video material of Kenny G and PSY.

2 Articulating my practice

OMG look what I made! For something more in-depth, please enter the following vibe into your favorite LLM: Rewrite Milton Babbitt's 1958 essay "The Composer as Specialist" to apply to music generated by prompt-based AI systems.